

5.6 PubMed数据的可视化分析

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李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

PUBMED

NIH National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

Log in

PubMed.gov

Advanced **1**

PubMed® comprises more than 34 million citations for biomedical literature from MEDLINE, life science journals, and online books. Citations may include links to full text content from PubMed Central and publisher web sites.

NIH National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

Log in

PubMed Advanced Search Builder

PubMed.gov
User Guide

Add terms to the query box **2**

MeSH Terms hypertension **ADD** Show Index

Query box
Enter / edit your search query here **3**

History and Search Details Download Delete

NIH National Library of Medicine
National Center for Biotechnology Information

Log in

PubMed Advanced Search Builder

PubMed.gov
User Guide

Add terms to the query box

MeSH Terms Enter a search term **AND** Show Index

Query box
hypertension[MeSH Terms] **Search** **4**

Save

Email

Send to

Sorted by: Publication date

Display options

MY NCBI FILTERS

307,850 results

Page 1 of 30,785

RESULTS BY YEAR

TEXT AVAILABILITY

- Abstract
- Free full text
- Full text

ARTICLE ATTRIBUTE

- Associated data

ARTICLE TYPE

- Books and Documents
- Clinical Trial **1**
- Meta-Analysis
- Randomized Controlled Trial
- Review
- Systematic Review

PUBLICATION DATE

- 1 year
- 5 years
- 10 years **2**
- Custom Range

Hypertension screening, awareness, treatment, and control: a study of their prevalence and associated factors in a nationally representative sample from Nepal.

Cite Dhungana RR, Pedisic Z, Dhimal M, Bista B, de Courten M.
Share Glob Health Action. 2022 Dec 31;15(1):2000092. doi: 10.1080/16549716.2021.2000092.
PMID: 35132939 [Free PMC article.](#)

0 View co-citations

Little syndrome misdiagnosed as primary aldosteronism is caused by inaccurate aldosterone-rennin detection while a novel *SCNN1G* mutation is discovered.

Cite Yang Y, Wu C, Qu D, Xu X, Chen L, Sun Q, Zhao X.
Share Blood Press. 2022 Dec;31(1):139-145. doi: 10.1080/08037051.2022.2088471.
PMID: 35723567

0 View co-citations

High blood pressure screening in pharmacies during May Measurement Month campaigns in Switzerland.

Cite Damianaki A, Theiler K, Beaney T, Wang W, Burnier M, Wuerzner G.
Share Blood Press. 2022 Dec;31(1):129-138. doi: 10.1080/08037051.2022.2086531.
PMID: 35699311

0 View co-citations

Quality of life following renal sympathetic denervation in treatment-resistant hypertensive patients: a two-year follow-up study.

Cite Hanssen TA, Subbotina A, Miroslawska A, Solbu MD, Steigen TK.
Share Scand Cardiovasc J. 2022 Dec;56(1):174-179. doi: 10.1080/14017431.2022.2084562.
PMID: 35686551

0 View co-citations

Thirty years with LIFE-a randomized clinical trial with more than 200 published

Save

Email

Send to **3**

Sorted by: Publication date

Display options

MY NCBI FILTERS

5,139 results

Page 1 of 514

RESULTS BY YEAR

Filters applied: Clinical Trial, in the last 10 years. Clear all

Thirty years with LIFE-a randomized clinical trial with more than 200 published articles on clinical aspects of left ventricular hypertrophy.

Cite Kjeldsen SE, Egan BM, Narkiewicz K, Kreutz R, Burnier M, Oparil S.
Share Blood Press. 2022 Dec;31(1):125-128. doi: 10.1080/08037051.2022.2083578.
PMID: 35674494 Clinical Trial. No abstract available.

1 View co-citations

TEXT AVAILABILITY

- Abstract
- Free full text
- Full text

ARTICLE ATTRIBUTE

- Associated data

ARTICLE TYPE

- Books and Documents
- Clinical Trial
- Meta-Analysis
- Randomized Controlled Trial
- Review
- Systematic Review

PUBLICATION DATE

- 1 year
- 5 years
- 10 years

Effects of the Mindfulness-Based Blood Pressure Reduction (MB-BP) program on depression and neural structural connectivity.

Cite Polcari JJ, Cali RJ, Nephew BC, Lu S, Rashkovskii M, Wu J, Saadeh F, Loucks E, King JA.
Share J Affect Disord. 2022 Aug 15;311:31-39. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2022.05.059. Epub 2022 May 17.
PMID: 35594968 Clinical Trial.

0 View co-citations

Blood pressure, antihypertensive drugs, and incident frailty: The Multidomain Alzheimer Preventive Trial (MAPT).

Cite Rouch L, Rolland Y, Hanon O, Vidal JS, Cestac P, Sallerin B, Andrieu S, Vellas B, Barreto PS; MAPT/DSA Group.
Share Maturitas. 2022 Aug;162:8-14. doi: 10.1016/j.maturitas.2022.03.001. Epub 2022 Mar 15.
PMID: 35489133 Clinical Trial.

0 View co-citations

PUBMED

hypertension[MeSH Terms]

Advanced Create alert Create RSS

Save Email **Send to**

Sorted by: Publication date

MY NCBI FILTERS

5,139 results

Page 1

RESULTS BY YEAR

TEXT AVAILABILITY

- Abstract
- Free full text
- Full text

ARTICLE ATTRIBUTE

- Associated data

ARTICLE TYPE

- Books and Documents
- Clinical Trial
- Meta-Analysis

Filters applied: Clinical Trial, in the last 10 years. Clear all

1 **Citation manager** - a randomized clinical trial with more than 30 years of follow-up effects of left ventricular hypertrophy.
Cite Kjeldsen SE, Egan BM, Narkiewicz K, Kreutz R, Burnier M, Oparil S. Blood Press. 2022 Dec;31(1):125-128. doi: 10.1080/08037051.2022.2083578. PMID: 35674494 Clinical Trial. No abstract available.

0 View co-citations

2 **A Randomized Open-Label Parallel-Group Study Comparing Safety of Cilnidipine and Amlodipine in Hypertensive Adults**
Cite Jj NK, D DC, Kavitha R. J Assoc Physicians India. 2022 Dec;69(12):11-12. PMID: 35057591 Clinical Trial.

1 View co-citations

3 **Effects of the Mindfulness-Based Blood Pressure Reduction on depression and neural structural connectivity.**
Cite Polcari JJ, Cali RJ, Nephew BC, Lu S, Rashkovskii M, Wu J, Saadeh F, Loucks E, J Affect Disord. 2022 Aug 15;311:31-39. doi: 10.1016/j.jad.2022.05.059. Epub 2022 Aug 15. PMID: 35594968 Clinical Trial.

hypertension[MeSH Terms]

Advanced Create alert Create RSS

Save Email Send to

Sorted by: Publication date

Create a file for external citation management software

Selection:

All results

2

Create file

Cancel

MY NCBI FILTERS

5,139 results

Page 1

RESULTS BY YEAR

TEXT AVAILABILITY

- Abstract

Filters applied: Clinical Trial, in the last 10 years. Clear all

1 **Thirty years with LIFE-a randomized clinical trial with more than 30 articles on clinical aspects of left ventricular hypertrophy.**
Cite Kjeldsen SE, Egan BM, Narkiewicz K, Kreutz R, Burnier M, Oparil S. Blood Press. 2022 Dec;31(1):125-128. doi: 10.1080/08037051.2022.2083578. PMID: 35674494 Clinical Trial. No abstract available.

0 View co-citations

2 **A Randomized Open-Label Parallel-Group Study Comparing the Safety and Efficacy of Cilnidipine and Amlodipine in Hypertensive Adults**

PUBMED

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
pubmed-hypertensi-set.nbib	2022/6/29 8:39	PubMed File	29,465 KB

名称	修改日期	类型	大小
download_1-5139.nbib	2022/6/29 8:39	PubMed File	29,465 KB

名称	修改日期	类型
data	2022/6/29 8:40	文件夹
data pubmed	2022/6/29 8:40	文件夹
project	2022/6/29 8:41	文件夹

CITESPACE

Check the Connection to MySQL@localhost

A problem encountered when attempting to connect your MySQL at localhost.

1. Make sure your MySQL server is on.
2. Make sure the following username and password in C:\Users\dell.citespace\mysql.ini are correct.

host: null
user: null
pass: null

CiteSpace: Data Processing Utilities

MySQL WOS Scopus Dimensions CNKI CSSCI MAG CSV PubMed

Database Project Edit Export Articles Authors Subject Categories Keywords/Phrases References Institutions History Burst Detection Semmed

Current Project
Project Name Count Records Select a query base

Warning: Queries with * are time-consuming. Execute them with the Search button.

Create a New Project
Input Directory Browse

Text Analysis
Term Extraction from Title and Abstract Fields
words: min max Extract Phrases Extract Verbs Summarize

Statistical Association Test
Phrase freq > Show Distributions p-level Log-Likelihood Show Graph

SQL Query and Results
SELECT count(*) FROM articles

Results of your SQL query will appear here.

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science Import/Export

Projects
 Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003)

Project Home: C:\Users\dell.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

Data Directory: C:\Users\dell.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 9 %

Space Status

Process Reports

Time Slicing
From 1993 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing
Term Source
 Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type
 Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Node Types
 Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category
 Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links
Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \in S} c_i k \in Z^+$
To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k =

Pruning Visualization
Pruning
 Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

CITESPACE

CiteSpace: Data Processing Utilities

MySQL WOS Scopus Dimensions CNKI CSSCI MAG CSV PubMed

Converting PubMed NBIB Formatted Files for CiteSpace 6/23/2021

On PubMed, search for records of interest and save results in NBIB formatted files as follows:

1. Choose the **Send to** option and select **Citation manager**
2. Save the NBIB file to the Input Directory
3. Start the conversion
4. Use the converted file in the output directory as input data files for CiteSpace

Mapping NBIB to the Web of Science (WoS) Format

NBIB Field	Example	WoS Field	Example
PMID	32701395	UT	32701395
OT	COVID-19	DE	COVID-19
MH	covid-19 vaccines/genetics/*immunology/*pharmacology	SC	covid-19 vaccines; genetics

Data Directories

Input Directory

Output Directory

Conversion Completed:
Records: 5139 Input Files: download_1-5139.nbib.

The Number of Records Converted in Total:
5139

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell - CO-DESC

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science

Projects

New hypertension More Actions ...

Project Home: D:\桌面\PUBMED\project

Data Directory: D:\桌面\PUBMED\data

GO! Stop Reset JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 22 %

Time Slicing

From 2012 JAN To 2022 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms

Space Status

Year	top	30	47	2	1/1
2012	top 30	47	2	1/1	
2013	top 30	438	35	92/92	
2014	top 30	446	35	74/74	
2015	top 30	575	45	93/93	
2016	top 30	589	31	66/66	
2017	top 30	671	32	87/87	
2018	top 30	578	48	93/93	
2019	top 30	616	52	101/101	
2020	top 30	532	42	96/96	
2021	top 30	548	35	69/69	
2022	top 30	169	17	17/17	

Node Types

Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

Select top 50 levels of most cited or occurred items from each slice.
Each level may include multiple qualified nodes.
The minimum level e is set in the project properties.

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks
 Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

Process Reports

44 Editorial
55924 Journal Article
484 Letter
44 News
11 Review

Parsing Time: 51 seconds
Total Run time: 7 seconds

Merged network: Nodes=120, Links=528
Exclusion List: 0
Network modeling ends at Wed Jun 29 09:02:23 CST 2022.

Your Options

? Project Title: hypertension

Time Frame: 2012-2022
Qualified Records: 5108

How do you like to proceed?

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	Keywords
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	573	0.00	2012	blood pressure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	134	0.00	2013	cardiovascular disease
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	111	0.00	2012	pulmonary hypertension
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	105	0.00	2013	randomized controlled trial
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	96	0.00	2013	clinical trial
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	54	0.00	2013	pulmonary arterial hyperten...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	53	0.00	2013	arterial stiffness
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	51	0.00	2013	heart failure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	50	0.00	2014	chronic kidney disease
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	50	0.00	2013	resistant hypertension
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	47	0.00	2013	risk factor
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	47	0.00	2013	renal denervation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	45	0.00	2013	essential hypertension
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	43	0.00	2013	ambulatory blood pressur...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40	0.00	2013	primary care
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40	0.00	2013	medication adherence
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.00	2013	ambulatory blood pressure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	36	0.00	2014	type 2 diabete
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	34	0.00	2013	antihypertensive agent
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	34	0.00	2014	diabetes mellitus
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2014	blood pressure variability
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2014	nitric oxide
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.00	2013	cardiovascular risk
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	28	0.00	2013	metabolic syndrome
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.00	2015	atrial fibrillation
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.00	2015	blood pressure control
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.00	2013	combination therapy
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	26	0.00	2014	left ventricular hypertrophy
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	24	0.00	2014	arterial hypertension
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	0.00	2013	endothelial function
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	0.00	2013	angiotensin receptor block...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	0.00	2014	heart rate
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	22	0.00	2014	physical activity
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.00	2013	calcium channel blocker
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.00	2013	systolic blood pressure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.00	2013	pulse wave velocity
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	20	0.00	2014	obstructive sleep apnea
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	20	0.00	2013	angiotensin-converting en...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2013	sympathetic nervous syste...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2015	african american
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	2014	type 2 diabetes mellitus
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2013	body mass index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2013	oxidative stress
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2014	uric acid
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2014	home blood pressure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2013	quality of life
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	14	0.00	2016	high blood pressure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	14	0.00	2014	angiotensin ii receptor blo...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	14	0.00	2013	glomerular filtration rate
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2016	randomised controlled trial
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2014	vitamin d
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2013	myocardial infarction
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2016	chronic thromboembolic p...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2018	older adult
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.00	2015	magnetic resonance imag...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.00	2014	randomized clinical trial
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	11	0.00	2015	chronic disease

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	Authors Institutions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	418	0.00	2012	Department of Cardiology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	370	0.00	2012	Department of Medicine
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	218	0.00	2012	Department of Internal Me...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	158	0.00	2012	Division of Cardiology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	135	0.00	2012	Department of Epidemiolo...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	131	0.00	2012	Department of Neurology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	107	0.00	2012	Division of Nephrology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	93	0.00	2012	Division of Cardiovasc...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	90	0.00	2012	Department of Cardiovasc...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	76	0.00	2012	Department of Nephrology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	71	0.00	2014	Department of Biostatistics
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	55	0.00	2013	Department of Pediatrics
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	52	0.00	2014	and.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	48	0.00	2014	School of Medicine
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	48	0.00	2013	Department of Obstetrics ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	46	0.00	2014	Division of Nephrology an...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40	0.00	2013	Department of Family Med...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40	0.00	2012	KARIO K
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	40	0.00	2014	Department of Radiology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	38	0.00	2013	Department of Anesthesio...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	36	0.00	2014	Department of Physiology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	36	0.00	2014	Department of Endocrinol...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	34	0.00	2014	School of Nursing
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.00	2014	Faculty of Medicine
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	33	0.00	2013	Department of Nephrology...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.00	2014	Department of Preventive ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.00	2014	School of Public Health
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.00	2012	ZHANG Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	31	0.00	2014	Department of Public Health
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2014	The George Institute for GI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2012	LI Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2012	Department of Pharmacol...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.00	2017	Division of General Interna...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.00	2015	Cardiology Department
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	29	0.00	2013	Department of Nutrition
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	27	0.00	2014	Department of Psychology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	24	0.00	2014	Cardiology Division
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	0.00	2015	Department of Pharmacy
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	23	0.00	2012	MANCIA G
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	22	0.00	2015	Cardiovascular Division
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	22	0.00	2014	Department of Psychiatry
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	22	0.00	2012	ZHANG J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.00	2015	Department of Emergency...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	21	0.00	2016	Department of Respiratory...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	20	0.00	2017	Division of Endocrinology
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	20	0.00	2012	WANG Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2012	WANG J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2019	Department of Biostatistic...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2012	CHEN J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	18	0.00	2013	Department of Medical On...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	2015	WANG X
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	2015	Department of Epidemiolo...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2014	Welch Center for Prevention
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2012	BÖHM M
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2012	ANDERSON C
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2012	SCHMIEDER R
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	15	0.00	2015	Assistance Publique-Hôpi...

CiteSpace, v. 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced
 June 29, 2022 at 9:14:40 AM CST
 PubMed: D:\桌面\PUBMED\data
 Timespan: 2012-2022 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBγ=-1, e=2.0
 Network: N=64, E=3066 (Density=0.0139)
 Largest CC: 602 (90%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None

Control Panel

Colormap | Burstness | Search | Clusters

Labels | Layout | Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold: 10

Font Size: 15

Node Size: 10

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold: 213

Font Size: 6

Node Size: 2

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size: 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold: 0

Font Size: 16

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length: 50

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

由于Pubmed数据质量问题，分析的机构和作者数据会存在较大的问题。

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	WoS Categories
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5094	0.00	2012	HUMANS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4411	0.00	2012	HYPERTENSION
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4293	0.00	2012	FEMALE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4150	0.00	2012	MALE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3742	0.00	2012	MIDDLE AGED
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2865	0.00	2012	AGED
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2505	0.00	2012	BLOOD PRESSURE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2194	0.00	2012	ADULT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1780	0.00	2012	ANTIHYPERTENSIVE AGE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1624	0.00	2012	DRUG THERAPY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1616	0.00	2012	TREATMENT OUTCOME
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1599	0.00	2012	DRUG EFFECTS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1291	0.00	2012	THERAPEUTIC USE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1240	0.00	2012	ADMINISTRATION & DOS...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1151	0.00	2012	COMPLICATIONS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1049	0.00	2012	METHODS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	972	0.00	2012	BLOOD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	949	0.00	2012	DOUBLE-BLIND METHOD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	808	0.00	2012	PROSPECTIVE STUDIES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	788	0.00	2012	DIAGNOSIS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	779	0.00	2012	EPIDEMIOLOGY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	739	0.00	2012	PHYSIOLOGY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	723	0.00	2012	RISK FACTORS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	634	0.00	2012	ADVERSE EFFECTS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	632	0.00	2012	FOLLOW-UP STUDIES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	621	0.00	2012	AGED, 80 AND OVER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	597	0.00	2012	BLOOD PRESSURE MONI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	544	0.00	2012	TIME FACTORS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	522	0.00	2012	YOUNG ADULT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	498	0.00	2012	PHYSIOPATHOLOGY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	465	0.00	2012	HYPERTENSION, PULMO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	416	0.00	2012	DRUG THERAPY, COMBI...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	416	0.00	2012	METABOLISM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	398	0.00	2012	ADOLESCENT
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	391	0.00	2012	PHARMACOLOGY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	340	0.00	2012	ETIOLOGY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	335	0.00	2012	DIABETES MELLITUS, TY...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	326	0.00	2012	CARDIOVASCULAR DISE...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	322	0.00	2012	BLOOD PRESSURE DET...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	318	0.00	2012	AMLODIPINE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	314	0.00	2012	CROSS-OVER STUDIES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	296	0.00	2012	BIOMARKERS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	287	0.00	2012	DOSE-RESPONSE RELA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	274	0.00	2012	HEART RATE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	271	0.00	2012	PREVENTION & CONTROL
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	266	0.00	2012	EXERCISE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	257	0.00	2012	CHEMICALLY INDUCED
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	256	0.00	2012	STATISTICS & NUMERICA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	251	0.00	2012	THERAPY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	245	0.00	2012	STROKE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	242	0.00	2012	TETRAZOLES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	242	0.00	2012	DIAGNOSTIC IMAGING
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	232	0.00	2012	BODY MASS INDEX
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	219	0.00	2012	OBESITY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	210	0.00	2012	MEDICATION ADHERENCE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	201	0.00	2012	CALCIUM CHANNEL BLO...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	198	0.00	2012	ESSENTIAL HYPERTENSI...

Spotlight Citation/Frequency Burst >>> Search: ti:q1 | fu:* # clusters 298

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold 10

Font Size 15

Node Size 10

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold 100

Font Size 2

Node Size 5

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold 0

Font Size 0

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length 50

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

#19 central arterial

#14 blood catecholamine level

#2 beneficial effect

#11 cerebral blood flow

#13 azilsartan medoxomil

#12 arterial stiffness

#6 sodium reduction

#7 pregnancy outcome

#16 direct renin inhibitor

#0 phase ii study

#5 genetic variant

#1 pharmacist intervention

#9 to-visit variability

#3 continuous positive airway pressure

#8 fixed-dose combination

#10 renal denervation

#4 pulmonary hypertension

#15 messaging intervention

#17 total stroke

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PubMed Mapping Tester

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hypertension

Search

'Old' PubMed Results

Count: 569,898

Mapping:

"hypertension"[MeSH Terms] OR "hypertension"[All Fields]

'New' PubMed Results

Count: 594,382 (4.3% difference)

Mapping:

"hypertense"[All Fields] OR "hypertension"[MeSH Terms] OR
"hypertension"[All Fields] OR "hypertension s"[All Fields] OR
"hypertensions"[All Fields] OR "hypertensive"[All Fields] OR
"hypertensive s"[All Fields] OR "hypertensives"[All Fields]

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